

RECONCILIATION, PUNISHMENT,
AND FRATERNAL CORRECTION

PAUL CHANDLER, O.CARM.

As part of the memorialisation of the work of Fr Xiberta on reconciliation in the Church, I was asked to explore the theme of reconciliation in the medieval Carmelite liturgical books. However, perhaps surprisingly, they proved to be an unpromising source.¹ The Constitutions of the Order, too, appear to be a dry well: there is no occurrence of the word *reconciliatio* or its cognates anywhere in the medieval Constitutions.² What does occur frequently, however, is the vocabulary of exclusion and punishment,³ which suggested to me that the search for processes of reconciliation in the historic life of the Order must be approached through their opposites. This approach means we must be prepared to take a strange journey into a mentality and culture not only very different from our own, but one we are likely to find disturbing and even repugnant: that is, the elaborate system of

¹ I have searched in *Missale Carmelitarum*, Brescia, Bonino de' Bonini, 1490; *Ordinaire de l'Ordre de Notre-Dame du Mont-Carmel, par Sibert de Beka vers 1312 publié d'après le manuscrit originel et collationné sur divers manuscrits et imprimés*, ed. BENEDICT ZIMMERMAN, *Bibliothèque Liturgique*, vol. 13 Paris, Picard, 1912; *Ceremoniale divini officii secundum Ordinem fratrum B. Virginis Mariae de Monte Carmeli: Ad normam novi missalis & breviarii compilatum, et Rmi. Patris Magistri Sebastiani Fantoni eiusdem Ordinis prioris generalis iussu aeditum* Romae: apud Gulielmum Faciottum, 1616; *Breviarium Carmelitarum noviter impressum*, [per... Baptistam Venetum de Cathaneis.. emendatum], Venice, Luca Antonii de Giunta, 1515; *Missale Fratrum Carmelitarum Ordinis Beatae Dei Genetricis Mariae, Capituli Generalis decreto... et... Sebastiani Fantoni Romani iussu denuo impressum et editum* Venice, apud Iuntas, 1621.

² *Corpus Constitutionum Ordinis Fratrum Beatissimae Virginis Mariae de Monte Carmelo. Volume Primo, 1281–1456*, ed. EDISON R.L. TINAMBUNAM and EMANUELE BOAGA, *Corpus Constitutionum Carmelitarum*, vol. 1 Rome, Edizioni Carmelitane, 2011.

³ I count ninety occurrences of cognates of *excommunicatio* in the Constitutions 1281–1465, and there is other relevant vocabulary especially relating to faults and punishment, which are very prominent concerns.

denunciation and punishment which was an omnipresent feature of medieval religious life.

A more or less systematic concern for admonishment and the correction of faults was already known in antiquity: for example, to Seneca and the Epicureans. Judaism and Islam also address issues related to correction,⁴ but in Christianity it attracted special attention because of the text of Matthew 18:15–17:

If another member of the church sins against you, go and point out the fault when the two of you are alone. If the member listens to you, you have regained that one. But if you are not listened to, take one or two others along with you, so that every word may be confirmed by the evidence of two or three witnesses. If the member refuses to listen to them, tell it to the church; and if the offender refuses to listen even to the church, let such a one be to you as a Gentile and a tax collector.

The public confession of faults was a feature of monastic life from the earliest times: Pachomius, Cassian, Basil, and Augustine all incorporate it as an ascetical and spiritual discipline, as do the various rules of the sixth and seventh centuries.⁵

The Rule of St Benedict provides for various forms of exclusion from the table and the choir in a long section (chs 23–30) about excommunication for faults, which include destructive attitudes such as defiance, disobedience, arrogance, and murmuring.⁶ Elsewhere concrete offences are named, among them damage to goods, violation of the silence, lateness for community acts, and abuse of authority.⁷ Depending on their seriousness, infractions brought a series of graduated disciplinary responses, from public admonishment, to forms of exclusion and excommunication, to physical punishment, with a view to the offender being brought to penitential sorrow and a resolution to make satisfaction for his fault. Unlike the Rule of the Master, where punishment is a retributive expression of law, Benedict's concern is more pastoral and medicinal, and he is explicit in acknowledging that the purpose of these disciplinary practices is

⁴ JEFFREY HAUSE, *Some Developments in the Medieval Practice of Fraternal Correction*, in *Irrtum-Error-Erreur*, ed. ANDREAS SPEER and MAXIME MAURIÈGE Berlin, De Gruyter, 2018, 529.

⁵ PHILIPPE SCHMITZ, *Chapitre des coupes*, in *Dictionnaire de Spiritualité*, vol. 2 Paris, Beauchesne, 1953, 2:483.

⁶ TERRENCE G. KARDONG, *Benedict's Rule: A Translation and a Commentary* Collegeville, Minn., Liturgical Press, 1996, 230–57.

⁷ *Ibid.*, 231.

personal conversion and reconciliation with the community whose life has been disrupted by the offender.⁸ The abbot “should focus all his attention on the care of wayward brothers, for *it is not the healthy but the sick who need a physician* (Mt 9:12)”. He is to seek the collaboration of “wise elderly brothers” to comfort the wavering brother, reaffirm the community’s continuing love and prayer for him, and urge him to make the satisfaction which will lead to reconciliation (ch. 27). Repeat offenders who refuse to change require harsher treatment: they are to be physically beaten, and at the same time the community’s prayer for them is to be redoubled. If all else fails, the incorrigible offender must be expelled, “for one sick sheep should not be allowed to infect the whole flock” (ch. 28).

Later in his Rule (chs 43–46) Benedict specifies forms of satisfaction for faults which will continue to be traditional in monastic discipline: exclusion from the table as a form of shaming, deprivation of wine, and the ritual humiliation of prostration both in choir and at the entrance to the chapel (ch. 44). For Benedict, self-denunciation of faults is the better option; those who require denunciation by others undergo a more severe penalty (ch. 46). Benedict, however, as is common in this whole disciplinary tradition, does not require public confession of matters of conscience: these are dealt with in private with the abbot or one of the spiritual seniors. In all this, his overriding concern is genuine healing, the restoration of the life of the community, and the deep conversion of the penitent.⁹

The modern reader is likely to be truly shocked at the thought of corporal punishment in the monastery which, however, remained a feature of monastic discipline into early modern times. Even in Roman antiquity corporal punishment had become associated especially with slaves and children, and the whip and the rod had become cultural symbols of servitude. Although the Roman *paterfamilias* had absolute authority to punish his household, it seems unlikely that beating was used on older children because it associated the family itself with a ritual of humiliation.¹⁰ Nevertheless, in the monastic context it seems that Roman notions of paternal authority met the biblical injunctions about physical punishment as an expression of love (Sir 30:1; Prov 23:14) and combined to make

⁸ Ibid., 253.

⁹ Ibid., 374–75.

¹⁰ JULIA HILLNER, *Monks and Children: Corporal Punishment in Late Antiquity*, *European Review of History: Revue Européenne d’Histoire* 16 (2009), 773–75.

physical punishment an ordinary feature of monastic life. However, corporal punishment was a last resort when other disciplinary measures had failed, or the offending conduct was irrational and therefore resistant to rational remedy.

There are some other elements of the medieval mentality which need to be taken into account if we are to have some understanding of how these disciplinary practices could work as elements of a healing and reconciling process. Katherine Allen Smith has encouraged us to think of it in the context of “the relationship between physical suffering and redemption that was central to medieval monastic ideals of spiritual progress and community”.

Inflicting pain upon oneself or others was not always considered cruel, and could even be an act of compassion under certain circumstances... Members of all the major religious orders viewed flogging as a necessary method of correction that required little or no justification... The penitential rituals... could equally serve to reinforce hierarchies, test humility and obedience, express compassion and love, and remind participants of Christ’s bodily suffering... The administration of discipline, done in the proper spirit, was an act of love in which there was no trace of cruelty... These elaborate symbolically-charged rites were designed to humble sinners and prepare them, body and spirit, for readmittance to the community of the faithful... No one doubted the spiritual efficacy of punishing sinners’ bodies; indeed, penitential logic insisted that it was cruel *not* to do so. Loving one’s neighbour sometimes required one to commit acts of violence against him.¹¹

In our post-Cartesian world we have lost the very lively sense that earlier generations had of the ineradicable connection of body and spirit and of the religious value of bodily suffering. Indeed, self-inflicted suffering is for us among the least comprehensible aspects of medieval piety: we are likely to see it as “a sign of a spiritual and psychological disorder and not, as was believed in the Middle Ages, of a proper and praiseworthy attitude toward oneself and God” and a source of grace.¹² Sickness and other forms of suffering in general were considered a grace and an opportunity to participate in the sufferings

¹¹ KATHERINE ALLEN SMITH, *Discipline, Compassion and Monastic Ideals of Community, c.950–1250* 2009, *Journal of Medieval History*, 35, 327–29, 533. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmedhist.2009.08.002>.

¹² GILES CONSTABLE, *Attitudes Toward Self-Inflicted Suffering in the Middle Ages*, The Ninth Stephen J. Brademas, Sr., Lecture Brookline, MA, Hellenic College Press, 1982, 7.

of Christ. So intertwined were body and soul that reconciliation with God was considered a first line of hospital treatment for bodily illness.¹³ We, however, can hardly see the physical punishment of others as anything but abusive and cruel.

These medieval disciplinary practices draw us in to a whole different world. Even King Henry II submitted to physical punishment by each of the eighty monks of Canterbury in 1174 in reparation for the murder of Thomas Becket. The Emperor Henry IV stood barefoot and hair-shirted for three days at Canossa in 1077 to beg for the absolution of his excommunication by Pope Gregory VII, and historians still debate whether the penitential ritual was humiliating or empowering for Henry.¹⁴

Some authors have seen these kinds of punitive disciplinary practices as expressions of social control in a Foucauldian totalitarian institution, but the cultural anthropologist Talal Asad has warned against a too-simple reduction of the complexities of these disciplinary rituals, which were not designed to intimidate individuals but rather to enable them to obtain spiritual mastery over their own inner life as a member of a community engaged in a life of conversion:

A remarkable feature of monastic discipline is that it explicitly aims to create, through a programme of communal living, the will to obey. The Christian monk who learns to will obedience is not merely someone who submits to another's will by force of argument or the threat of force—or simply by way of habitual, unthinking response. He is not someone who has 'lost his own will', as though a man's will could be 'truly' his only when it remained opposed to another's. The obedient monk is a person for whom obedience is *his* virtue—in the sense of being his ability, potentiality, power—a Christian virtue developed through discipline. This is certainly one important difference between the medieval monastery and other 'total institutions', such as prisons and hospitals, with which the monastery has, sometimes been classified (Goffman, 1961). The point is not that force has no necessary place in monasteries—of course it has. It is that force is a crucial element in a particular transformation of dispositions, not merely in the keeping of order among inmates... In the

¹³ JESSALYN BIRD, *Medicine for Body and Soul: Jacques de Vitry's Sermons to Hospitallers and Their Charges*, in *Religion and Medicine in the Middle Ages*, ed. PETER BILLER and JOSEPH ZIEGLER, York Studies in Medieval Theology, vol. 3 York, York Medieval Press, 2001, 103.

¹⁴ SARAH HAMILTON, *Penance in the Age of the Gregorian Reform*, in *Retribution, Repentance, and Reconciliation: Papers Read at the 2002 Summer Meeting and the 2003 Winter Meeting of the Ecclesiastical History Society*, ed. KATE COOPER and JEREMY GREGORY, Studies in Church History, vol. 40 Woodbridge, Boydell Press, 2004, 73.

context of the medieval monastic programme it was a disciplinary technique for the self to create a desire for obedience to the Law—but that was intrinsic to what the self was, not an instrument to be used by Authority to keep an already-constituted self in order.¹⁵

Flogging, like the milder forms of monastic discipline, took place in refectory or chapter in the presence of the whole community, who were therefore participants in a penitential drama of complex dimensions: “monastic superiors displayed their authority, sinful monks proclaimed their obedience and humility (or their pride and disobedience, if they refuse to submit), and other members of the community modelled the virtue of compassion for their fallen brothers.”¹⁶ Indeed, medieval religious were members of an “emotional community”, where the disciplines of daily life functioned as strategies for fostering and disciplining the affective and emotional life in directions which promoted the inner dispositions for spiritual growth. Disciplinary rituals called on everyone to be a participant in a journey of personal conversion supported by the total life of the community.

We need to recall as well that corporal punishment was only one element in a much more elaborate penitential process of repentance, conflict resolution, and reintegration. The experience of monastic life itself would have taught that conversion and reconciliation are often not achieved quickly after communion is ruptured. Our attention tends to be drawn to the most imposing and dramatic moments in situations of conflict or failure, and rarely to the long-term nature of the ritualised life of a religious community, with its repetitive processes and daily rituals. Punishments, ceremonial humiliations, and ritual separations from the common life extended over short or long periods were designed to offer both the offender and the community the opportunity to engage with the need for forgiveness, reconciliation and the rebuilding of trust. Penance had to have a remedial effect, which in turn required an interiorisation not always easy or quick to achieve for any of the parties. Short-term punishment, therefore, had to be combined with long-term ritual. Only the first is usually recorded and so distorts our sense of the mechanics of penance

¹⁵ TALAL ASAD, *On Ritual and Discipline in Medieval Christian Monasticism*, in *Economics and Society* 16:2 (1987), 159, 192. JANE SAYERS, *Violence in the Medieval Cloister*, in *Journal of Ecclesiastical History* 41:4 (1990), 533–42, is more sympathetic to the view that the monastery is an implicitly violent “total institution”.

¹⁶ SMITH, *Discipline, Compassion and Monastic Ideals of Community*, 337.

and conflict resolution in “low-key practices, pious repetitiveness, willing obedience, and the continual exercise of virtue”.¹⁷

St Benedict envisaged expulsion from the community as the ultimate sanction on the incorrigible monk, but by the thirteenth century the abandonment of religious vows was considered impossible. Apostate religious were reported to royal or civic authorities and, if apprehended, were arrested and returned to their community.¹⁸ This conviction of the irreversibility of religious profession entailed a consequence unthinkable to us, the monastic prison, in which reluctant religious were confined, even permanently.¹⁹ We need not abandon our dismay at the fate of imprisoned religious, however; to take account of the very different context in which the medieval monastic prison was understood. The monastery itself had been long understood as a metaphorical prison,²⁰ and “a long tradition [from the sixth century] of detaining non-monastics within monasteries, too, underpinned ideas of the monastic site as a space for not only incarceration but also penance, healing and the articulation of humility.”²¹

Prison was used as the ultimate step in the graded punishments for the most severe and disruptive offences against monastic community. Cluny from the eleventh century used imprisonment for offences such as perjury, apostasy, talking to women, and owning property, as well as more minor but nevertheless disruptive offences such as quarrelling, drunkenness, and abusive language. By the thirteenth century imprisonment was a standard punishment among

¹⁷ TJAMKE SNIJDERS and STEVEN VANDERPUTTEN, *From Scandal to Monastic Penance: A Reconciliatory Manuscript from the Early Twelfth-Century Abbey of St. Laurent in Liège*, in *Church History* 82:3 (2013), 524–25.

¹⁸ F. DONALD LOGAN, *Runaway Religious in Medieval England, c. 1240–1540*, Cambridge Studies in Medieval Life and Thought, 4th series Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1996.

¹⁹ ANNE JACOBSON SCHUTTE, *By Force and Fear: Taking and Breaking Religious Vows in Early Modern Europe*, Ithaca, Cornell University Press, 2011; MEGAN CASSIDY-WELCH, *Incarceration and Liberation: Prisons in the Cistercian Monastery*, in *Viator* 32 (2001), 23–42; ULRICH LEHNER, *Monastic Prisons and Torture Chambers: Crime and Punishment in Central European Monasteries, 1600–1800* Eugene, Or., Cascade Books, 2013; TERRENCE KARDONG, *People Storage: Mabillon’s Diatribe Against Monastic Prisons*, in *Cistercian Studies* 26 (1991), 40–57.

²⁰ JEAN LECLERCO, *Le cloître, est-il un prison?*, in *Revue d’ascétique et de la mystique* 47 (1971), 407–420; J.M. FERRANTE, *Images of the Cloister: Haven or Prison?*, in *Medievalia* 12 (1989), 57–66.

²¹ CASSIDY-WELCH, *Incarceration and Liberation*, 24.

religious orders: the Cistercians from 1206, the Dominicans from 1238, the Carthusians from 1261, but it has a strong element of penitence, at least partly linked to the new culture of guilt after Lateran IV.²² The Carmelites made provision for the monastic prison from the first extant Constitutions in 1281.²³

We have been talking about the conspicuous extremes of the penitential system of medieval religious life, and it is necessary to go back to the beginning and place these extremes in a broader context. The Dominicans since 1236 had asserted that their Constitutions, as merely human law, did not bind under pain of sin, and the Carmelites followed.²⁴ This decision against the “strong obedience” claimed in older monastic rules and authority structures was no doubt intended as a liberation, but it may have been in some ways counter-productive. Dominic “presupposed generosity”²⁵ and conscientiousness, but if they were not forthcoming, sanctions and enforcement must have seemed the only practical alternative in the management of undisciplined persons and destructive behaviours. An elaborate system of punishments for infractions therefore came to reinforce the culture of obedience, based in turn on the ancient monastic traditions which we have been considering. The statutes of the Premonstratensians, which exercised considerable influence on Dominican legislation and on that of the other mendicant orders, devoted the third of its four sections to a classification of faults and their appropriate punishments.²⁶ To a large extent the early Carmelite Constitutions adopted the correctional system developed by the Premonstratensians; the Dominicans developed it in even more detail.²⁷

In the culture of obedience of the medieval Constitutions there is barely a regulation which does not prescribe the consequences of the failure to observe it, with specified graduated punishments, the *culpae*,

²² *Ibid.*, 28–31, 38.

²³ 1281:37; CCC 1:74.

²⁴ SIMON TUGWELL, ed., *Early Dominicans: Selected Writings*, Classics of Western Spirituality New York, Paulist Press, 1982, 22–23; MICHAEL VARGAS, *Weak Obedience, Undisciplined Friars, and Failed Reforms in the Medieval Order of Preachers*, in *Viator* 42:1 (2011), 289–90.

²⁵ TUGWELL, *Early Dominicans*, 22–23.

²⁶ *Les Statuts de Prémontré réformés sur les ordres de Grégoire IV et d’Innocent IV au XIIIe siècle*, ed. PL. F. LEFÈVRE, Bibliothèque de la Revue d’Histoire Ecclésiastique, vol. 13 Louvain, Bureaux de la Revue, 1946, 65–82.

²⁷ RAYMOND CREYTENS, ed., *Les Constitutions des Frères Prêcheurs dans la rédaction de S. Raymond de Peñafort 1241*, in *Archivum Fratrum Praedicatorum* 18 (1948), 5–68.

which were light, medium, grave, graver, and very grave, extending from reprimand to imprisonment.²⁸

A light *culpa* is associated with a fault such as reading or singing badly in the Office and not making an immediate act of humility by placing a hand on the ground, or mistreating books or clothing. It calls for a mild penance such as the recitation of a psalm or three *Pater nosters*.²⁹

A medium *culpa* concerns such matters as fooling around in church (*si quis... inordinate se habuerit, vel levitatem mentis ostendit*); idle chatter or dirty jokes (*si quis turpem sermonem vel vaniloquium in usum habuerit*); calling someone to one's cell without permission; or neglecting assigned duties; and so on. The penalty is corporal punishment ("the discipline") and as many psalms as the community chapter imposes. Habitual actions of the kind mean the medium fault becomes a grave one.³⁰

The grave fault is associated more with habitual problems: quarrelling; resistance to community discipline; acceptance of gifts of clothing and the like without permission; unseemly conduct with women which draws suspicion; habitual infringement of silence, or swearing, or breaking of the fast; inability to admit one's faults; disorderly conduct in general. Such things are punished by the discipline twice in chapter and a two-day fast on bread and water, and the confiscation of goods illicitly received, with the doubling of penalties for those in need of severer punishment.³¹

The graver fault (*gravior culpa*) involves contumaciousness or rebelliousness, and such offences as insubordination, detraction, dishonesty, and drunkenness. These bring not only personalised punishment but the traditional ostracism, confinement in the cell, and ritualised humiliation in the refectory and chapel: the offender must eat his bread and water from the floor, and prostrate himself at the door of the chapel so that the community must step over him. These punishments are intended to be medicinal: they continue until he comes back by means of repentance (*nisi per poenitentiam redierit*).³²

²⁸ I expand here on an earlier treatment in PAUL CHANDLER, *Liturgy and the Carmelite Constitutions, 1281–1930*, in *Fons et culmen vitae carmelitanae: Proceedings of the Carmelite Liturgical Seminar, S. Felice del Benaco, 13–16 June 2006*, Textus et Studia Historica Carmelitana, vol. 30 Rome, Edizioni Carmelitane, 2007, 75–104.

²⁹ 1294:43; CCC 1:112.

³⁰ 1294:44; CCC 1:113.

³¹ 1294:45; CCC 1:113.

³² 1294:46; CCC 1:113–114.

Were these punishments cruel means of asserting control of the individual members of a community? That is no doubt at least partly true, but contemporaries saw them as a struggle for a person's imperilled soul. It is for this reason that the prior—again in the spirit of a long tradition—is exhorted to care for the brother who is suffering punishment for a graver fault. He is to monitor his state of mind lest he give way to despair, and after two or three days he is to send some senior brothers to plead with the wrongdoer that he do penance humbly, to encourage him through their compassion, and to help by their intercession.³³ At this level, particularly, the life of a community with its most challenging and difficult members is raised from a level of mere management to one that is directly connected to conversion and reconciliation and which is expressed, at least in its idealism, as a sort of liturgy of repentance.

The gravest fault is explicitly defined, not illustrated by examples as are the others: *Gravissima culpa est incorrigibilitas*. It is the incorrigibility of the person who does not fear to commit fault and yet refuses to do penance: the penalty is imprisonment imposed by the prior general or provincial, or the general or provincial chapter, until he comes to his senses. And since his actions are contrary to his profession, he is to be deprived of the sign of it (the habit).³⁴

The system of the *culpae* gave birth to the chapter of faults (*capitulum culparum*), in which the brethren were expected to confess their own faults and even to denounce those of others, both as an act of personal humility and so that the superior could correct them. Denunciation, it is clear, was not considered cruel; it was cruel, rather, to neglect the Christian duty to admonish the sinner and assist him in the journey of conversion.³⁵

In fact, the process of fraternal correction became associated with church renewal³⁶ and attracted lively spiritual and theological interest from the twelfth century on from some of the greatest theological

³³ Ibid. "Ipse tamen prior ne in desperationem labi possit, secunda die vel tertia et etiam alias quando sibi videtur expedire, mittat ad eum seniores qui moneant ad poenitentiam humiliter faciendam, foveant per compassionem et adiuvent per suam intercessionem."

³⁴ 1294:47; CCC 1:114-115.

³⁵ ÉLISABETH LUSSET, 'Excessus delinquentium in capitulo proclamantur'. Dénoncer le crime au sein des monastères au Moyen Age XIIe-XVe siècle, in *Dénoncer le crime du Moyen Age au XIXe siècle*, ed. MARTINE CHARAGEAT and MATHIEU SOULA Pessac, Maison des Sciences de l'Homme d'Aquitaine, 2014, 27-29.

³⁶ EDWIN D. CRAUN, *Ethics and Power in Medieval English Reformist Writing*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2010.

thinkers of the era: Alexander of Hales, Hugh of St Cher, Albert the Great, and Thomas Aquinas. An early concern to enable the correction of superiors by subordinates gave way to an emphasis on the role of fraternal correction as an act of mutual charity, as a guarantor of common life, and a path for the reintegration of offenders into the community they had disrupted. For the friars, fraternal correction also became linked to their principal missionary concerns: preaching reform of life, promoting spiritual growth, and cultivating the interior consciousness that would be expressed in confession. They distinguished between fraternal correction, which is non-coercive, grounded in charity, and the responsibility of every Christian, and judicial correction, which includes coercion and punishment, is grounded in justice, and exercised only by those who hold office.³⁷

They were quite aware of the shadow side of correction: that it could degenerate into self-righteousness, vigilantism, spying, vengeance and pettiness, and were concerned that the practice be integrated into an ideal of charity and virtue: fraternal correction must be judicious, gentle, and come from charity and compassion, not malice or mockery, says Hugh of St Cher.³⁸ Albert the Great regards it as the most important work of charity, and sets out the conditions: no hypocrisy, no publication of a private failing, openness to the possibility of change, without indignation, derision or indictment.³⁹ Aquinas lists occasions when fraternal correction will not achieve its aim and so should not proceed: if it incites hatred rather than reform, causes scandal, fails to respect social difference, is insensitive to its effect, or is mere busyboddiness; it must be motivated by charity and the corrector must be suited to the task, or the result will be harm and even violence.⁴⁰

So there is a sophisticated consciousness of the idealism represented by the practice of fraternal correction and the possibilities of its dysfunction. Hause summarises:

... the unfolding understanding of fraternal correction in the thirteenth century is neither anti egalitarian nor dangerously inquisitorial. It is the story of a practice, based in a precept of love, expressing one neighbor's

³⁷ TAKASHI SHOGIMEN, *From Disobedience to Toleration: William of Ockham and the Medieval Discourse on Fraternal Correction*, in *Journal of Ecclesiastical History* 52:4 (2001), 599–622.

³⁸ HAUSE, *Some Developments*, 533–34.

³⁹ *Ibid.*, 535.

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*, 536.

genuine concern for the happiness of another. The understanding of how that practice is integrated into the larger ethics of charity and moral virtue grows richer as thinkers reflect more about both the practice and ethics, and the restrictions and conditions on the practice themselves grow out of that richer understanding and further reflection. Nevertheless tensions remain that thirteenth-century thinkers did not adequately address. These tensions concern not the initial stage of fraternal correction, but those later stages that operate by inducing shame and fear into the sinner to be corrected...⁴¹

Of course, the chapter of faults lasted into living memory, but largely as an empty ritual sometimes imposed only on novices. It had long ago lost its substantial functions as a means of promoting religious observance, preserving harmony in community, inviting all to individual and communal conversion, and providing a mechanism for the reconciliation and reintegration of the repentant into the life of the community. There are many cultural reasons for its disappearance. As I have remarked elsewhere:

The mentality of the *culpa*e and the practice of the chapter of faults (*capitulum culparum*) has become particularly difficult for us to comprehend from the standpoints of many of our modern cultures. Delumeau has made us aware of the destructive effects of the culture of guilt which attained especially strong character in the late Middle Ages and in the Reformation era: "one of the prime obsessions of Western civilization, a concern of all people, from the theologians to the most modest peasants".⁴² A. Gauthier has noted that even in the Middle Ages the psychological effects of the *capitulum culparum* as a practice had a certain ambiguity. Medieval religious were aware of the danger of scruple in the face of complex sets of regulations governing the whole of life. Gauthier mentions the example of St Dominic who declared at the Bologna chapter that he would rather go through convents and cut up all the rules with a knife than have them make the brothers scrupulous.⁴³ However, even the forms of ritualised humiliation which seem most unpalatable to us, are at a certain level meant to be understood as quasi-liturgical forms, symbolisations of a community on a journey between weakness and healing.⁴⁴

⁴¹ Ibid., 537–38.

⁴² JEAN DELUMEAU, *Sin and Fear: The Emergence of a Western Guilt Culture 13th-18th Centuries*, trans. Eric Nicholson New York, St. Martin's Press, 1990, 248.

⁴³ A. GAUTHIER, *Colpa*, in *Dizionario degli Istituti di Perfezione* 2 1973, 1238.

⁴⁴ CHANDLER, *Liturgy and the Carmelite Constitutions*, 82–83.

In fairly recent times there have been some attempts to reanimate the idealism of the chapter of faults as a means of repairing whatever ruptures of communion are caused by failures to commit to the demands of a life of charity in community. Gabriel Ghislain has made an eloquent plea for this traditional practice as “a workshop of the Holy Spirit”, an essential help to true communion rather than “a juxtaposition of isolations”, an expression of disinterested love for the other and of human reciprocity in the shared journey of evangelical conversion.⁴⁵ But such attempts have probably had very little resonance.

It is rather the sexual abuse crisis that has once more put fraternal correction on the map. Boniface Ramsey, for example, has called the case of ex-Cardinal Theodore McCarrick, whose sexualised behaviour with seminarians continued for decades, gossiped about but never called to account, “a failure of fraternal correction”:

McCarrick’s brazenness and lack of shame, his indifference to what others who knew of his behavior might have thought of him (and he ought to have known that they knew), are shocking enough. The fact that those who knew about at least some of his misconduct did not shun him—that he was accepted and even fêted by his peers—is every bit as shocking. There is talk now of a mechanism to address malfeasance in the hierarchy. Would I be naïve if I said that such a mechanism already exists and that its classic name is fraternal correction?... The case of Theodore McCarrick is, among other things, a case of the failure of fraternal correction.⁴⁶

McCarrick’s failings were particularly grave, and received deservedly grave punishment when they were eventually brought to justice. But it is not hard to think of smaller-scale failings of mutual support and fraternal correction in our own lives. Faced with a community member who is troubled, dysfunctional, or disruptive we face cultural barriers to what were once considered the spiritual works of mercy: admonishing the sinner, instructing the ignorant, counseling the doubtful. Reluctance to interfere becomes resignation, resignation becomes enabling, enabling can become complicity, and complicity can become codependence, all marked by a sense of helplessness.

⁴⁵ GABRIEL GHISLAIN, *Le chapitre des coupes signe de communion*, in *Collectanea Cisterciensia* 27 (1965), 178–93.

⁴⁶ BONIFACE RAMSEY, *The Case of Theodore McCarrick: A Failure of Fraternal Correction*, *Commonweal* 16 February 2019.

Modern religious life, no longer marked by the medieval concern for total uniformity of external observance, and many modern cultures focused on individual autonomy and personal responsibility, can function as barriers to effective concern for the common life of a community, and even sometimes as a barrier to our pastoral care for one another. Reconciliation, in its multiform dimensions, can become a casualty.

John Braithwaite, the prominent theorist of the restorative justice movement, has invited us to distinguish between disintegrative or stigmatising shaming and reintegrative shaming.⁴⁷ The medieval system of faults, unpalatable as we may find it, was a system of reintegrative shaming: its rituals of disgrace and punishment, ostracism and even imprisonment, were all oriented to forgiveness, restoration, reconciliation and reintegration. Condemnation was directed at behaviour rather than persons, whose failings were presumed to be the weaknesses of a fundamentally good person who could be redirected into the path of evangelical life in the Body of Christ. Much twenty-first century shaming, however, is harsh and stigmatising: there is little recognition of the possibilities of redemption, or distinction between behaviour and person, or possibility of forgiveness. It is a different and crueller dynamic than the public penance of the early Church, of which the monastic processes we have seen are a subset:

The welcoming of penitents on Holy Thursday offers a striking image of reintegrative shaming. Their penance is painful enough to satisfy justice, unchosen enough to avoid self-absorption—and it ends in a restoration of community. A medieval Maundy Thursday offered striking visual imagery of hope and healing, which reminded everyone that public penitents remained a part of the body of Christ.⁴⁸

Even modern corporate group dynamic theory now recognises the need for the kinds of processes which were incorporated into medieval religious life: apology, substantive penance, participation of the injured in the process of resolution, forgiveness, and reconciliation:

The data also invite new conceptualizations of the dynamics of forgiveness, penance, and reconciliation. Because conflict is an inevitable human state, violated expectations are a normal part of interpersonal

⁴⁷ *Crime, Shame and Reintegration*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1989.

⁴⁸ EVE TUSHNET, *The Case for Public Penance: An Ancient Church Practice Offers Lessons for the Age of Clerical Abuse, Mass Incarceration and #MeToo, America* 220:5 4 March 2019, 29–34.

interaction. This study suggests that acknowledging responsibility for a harmful act can be quite effective in starting the process of reconciliation, especially when denial might prompt disbelief. Voluntary substantive offers of penance seem to provide particularly clear and strong foundations for rebuilding cooperation.⁴⁹

No one, I think, would propose the restoration of the medieval system of *culpa*e and punishment, nor the traditional chapter of faults. They belong to the past and in most of our modern cultures would be simply impossible. Nevertheless, we can ask what we might learn from the medieval approach to the complexities of life and interpersonal relations in community, an approach which had no illusions about the destructive potential of human weaknesses, large and small, but still espoused a lofty idealism which aspired, even in the face of repeated failure, to the ongoing reconciliation of individuals with God and one another in a community of fraternal love. It was never an easy process nor one without its own dangers, but it was supported by institutional structure, well-tested criteria, and a culture of mercy.

It is not easy to see how these ideals might be re-imagined and given concrete expression in a very different age, but we have seen the dire consequences of replacing the open culture of fraternal correction and public penance with a culture of silence, autonomy and non-interference. The crisis of our own time is an invitation to re-imagine ways in which a shared commitment to personal conversion and a common regard for the necessary discipline of life together might again become an expression of mutual care and a deep openness to ongoing reconciliation with one another.

⁴⁹ WILLIAM P. BOTTOM, et al., *When Talk is not Cheap: Substantive Penance and Expressions of Intent in Rebuilding Cooperation*, in *Organization Science* 13:5 (2002), 511.